

UDC: 636.0.82.933

**BIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SUR SHEEP BELONGING TO
DIFFERENT GROUPS*****Kalimbetova Aynura Kosherbay qızı****Master's Student,**Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine,
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Abstract. *The biological features of the Karakalpak Sur Karakul sheep bred in the Takhtakupyr district are presented in this study. The research aimed to investigate how these biological and ethological characteristics affect the growth, development, and productive qualities of sheep and their offspring under the specific ecological and climatic conditions of the northwestern Kyzylkum desert. Particular attention was given to live weight dynamics, adaptability, and the relationship between environmental factors and productivity indicators.*

The results demonstrated that sheep belonging to different ethological types show significant variation in biological traits, including body weight, constitution, and adaptive potential. Sheep of the first ethological type exhibited the highest live weight and more stable productivity throughout the breeding and grazing seasons compared to other groups. This advantage is explained by their better feed activity and adaptation to extreme desert conditions, characterized by high summer temperatures and severe winter cold.

The findings provide valuable insights into the biological diversity of Sur Karakul sheep and highlight the importance of selective breeding based on ethological types to enhance productivity. Practical recommendations are proposed for the effective utilization of the genetic potential of Karakalpak Sur Karakul sheep to improve reproductive performance and increase the efficiency of sheep breeding in arid regions.

Key words. *Karakul sheep, Sur Karakul type, biological characteristics, ethological types, productivity indicators, live weight dynamics, adaptability, genetic potential, offspring performance, reproductive traits, breeding efficiency, desert environment, selection and improvement.*

(8th international scientific and practical conference)

Relevance of the Topic. Karakul sheep breeding is one of the important branches of livestock farming in the republic. Karakul sheep, which form the basis of this sector, are well adapted to about 20.0 million hectares of desert pastures characterized by extreme conditions. The primary product of these sheep, the Karakul pelt, is considered unique in the world due to its color, variety, and ornamental patterns.

The valuable characteristics of Karakul sheep have led to their spread and breeding in more than 40 countries. Among them are Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, the Republic of South Africa, Namibia and Afghanistan, where Karakul breeding is well developed.

In the Commonwealth countries, including the Republic of Kalmykia (Russia), Ukraine and Moldova, Karakul sheep are also bred.

In these regions, extensive research has been carried out to improve the heredity, expand the gene pool, and enhance the productivity and genetic traits of Karakul sheep, leading to the development of valuable genotypes with diverse colors and fleece patterns.

Research Objective. The objective of this study was to investigate the ethological and biological characteristics of the Karakalpak Sur Karakul sheep bred in the northwestern Kyzylkum region, to assess how these characteristics influence the formation and manifestation of productivity in sheep and their offspring, and to determine effective methods to increase productivity.

Research Methods. The lamb pelts obtained from the experimental sheep were evaluated according to the “Guidelines for Conducting Breeding Work and Evaluation (Bonitation) in Karakul Sheep Breeding.”

The numerical data were statistically analyzed using the methods of variation statistics described in “A Guide to Biometry for Zootechnicians.” [1,2]

Livestock breeds differ in their biological characteristics, which play a key role in their adaptability to breeding conditions and in achieving maximum productivity under specific environmental conditions.

Therefore, identifying the biological characteristics of animals is essential for studying their adaptability and productivity potential.

It is known that Karakul sheep are a desert-adapted breed that graze almost year-round.

The desert’s harsh conditions—feed and water scarcity, and a sharply continental climate (up to +50 °C in summer and –25 °C in winter)—have shaped a complex of unique anatomical, physiological, and exterior traits in Karakul sheep.

According to literature sources, all livestock species, including Karakul sheep, possess biological indicators related to both interior and exterior characteristics, including live weight, body measurements, body conformation indices, constitutional types, and vitality.

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Based on these factors, research was conducted to study certain biological indicators in sheep and their offspring belonging to different ethological types.

Live Weight. The live weight of Karakul sheep is one of the main indicators that determine their physiological condition, growth, development, fatness, body size, and productivity. This trait depends on many factors, including sex, age, breed, body constitution, feeding, and breeding conditions.

Studies have shown that live weight can also be related to ethological types. However, this aspect has not been sufficiently studied in Karakul sheep.

Research Results. Taking these aspects into account, during the study the dynamics of live weight in sheep of different ethological types were examined across the main seasons. The results are summarized in the following table.

Table 1

Dynamics of live weight in sheep across seasons

Ethological type of sheep	Live weight, kg								
	After birth			After the lambs are separated			Before the trip		
	n	X±Sx	Cv	n	X±Sx	Cv	n	X±Sx	Cv
I	30	36,85±0,43	6,28	30	39,95±0,50	6,65	30	41,88±0,52	6,72
II	30	35,45±0,42 ^x	6,37	30	38,60±0,48 ^x	6,68	30	40,25±0,50 ^x	6,70
III	30	33,10±0,47 ^x	6,83	30	36,40±0,50 ^{x)}	7,40	30	38,80±0,51 ^{x)}	7,05

From the data, it can be seen that in all seasons, sheep of the first ethological type showed superiority in live weight.

After lambing, their average live weight was 36.85 ± 0.43 kg, which was 1.36 kg higher than that of the second type ($P < 0.05$) and 3.73 kg higher than that of the third type ($P < 0.001$).

After the lambs were separated, the live weight was 39.95 ± 0.50 kg in the first type, 38.60 ± 0.48 kg in the second and 36.40 ± 0.50 kg in the third. The difference between the first and second types was 1.3 kg ($P < 0.05$), and between the first and third types – 3.58 kg ($P < 0.001$).

By the mating period, the live weight increased further, and the first ethological type of sheep maintained statistically significant superiority ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.001$) over the second and third types.

Conclusion. The analysis of the table shows that, compared to the third ethological type, the second type of sheep also had a statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) higher live weight.

The observed differences and statistically reliable advantages can be explained by differences in feeding activity among the various ethological types of sheep.

Practical Recommendations. As one of the main means of efficient use of desert areas, the Karakul sheep industry requires maximizing its productivity.

Based on this research, it is recommended to use the identified biological characteristics of different ethological types of Karakalpak Sur Karakul sheep to enhance the productivity of the breed and its offspring by applying the most effective breeding and management strategies.

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